

Ecological Discourses in Indian English Fiction

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Ms.T.Thenmozhi, M.A., M.Phil., (Ph.D.),,

Assistant Professor of English

*Vivekanandha College for Women (Affiliated To Periyar University, Salem)
Unjanai, Tiruchengode*

Dr.T.S.Geetha, M.A., M.Phil., Ph.D., PGDJMC.,

Associate Professor of English

*J.K.K. Nattraja College of Arts & Science
Natarajapuram, Komarapalayam*

Abstract

This research paper aims to learn the ecocritical aspects in the fiction of Indian authors like Bhabani Bhattacharya, Kamala Markandaya, Amitav Ghosh, Raja Rao, R.K.Narayan, Ruskin Bond, and Anita Desai. Since ages literature is well known for sparkly society, current issues and human activities. There is a profusion of research which uses nature and scenery as its background. Man and nature interrelate on different levels, helpful or equally destructive. At the same time, the permanent intrusion of man in natural activities has posed a hazard both to himself and to the atmosphere. If this is not attended to, it will guide to irreversible damage.

Keywords: Ecocriticism, contemporary issues, society, Indian fiction.

Literature and environment are always entangled in a strong association, as is evident in the works of writers throughout the ages. The realization of writers has brought the two disciplines, ecology and literature, collectively again and again. Their aim has been respecting nature as a guide, protector, and mother (Wordsworth), as a supernatural force (Coleridge), or in more modern texts to accumulate the earth's environment which is being damaged due to man's mishandling.

Work has been completed on ecocriticism or 'green studies' in the USA and UK. For ecocritics, the nineteenth-century developments in literature are essential. American and British Romantic writers took a fastidious concentration in nature as a theme. Henry David Thoreau's *Walden* (1854) and Ralph Waldo Emerson's *Nature* (1836) are the defining works in the meadow of ecocriticism. Don DeLillo, a modern American author, has in his *Underworld* (1988) highlighted the subject of managing to dump of waste which is leading to the descent of the environment. If we glance into the history of Indian literature, we discover many well-known writers contributing to this track.

The word 'ecocriticism' was first used by William Rueckert in his essay "Literature and Ecology: An Experiment in Ecocriticism" in

1978. He defines ecocriticism as “the application of ecology and ecological concepts to the study of literature because ecology (as a science, as a discipline, as the basis for human vision) has the greatest relevance to the present and future of the world” (1996:107). Peter Barry added a chapter titled “Ecocriticism” to the second edition of his *Beginning Theory: An Introduction to Literary and Cultural Theory* (1995). Thomas K. Dean considers Eco-criticism as “a study of culture and cultural products (artworks, writings, scientific theories, etc.)... in some way is connected with the human relationship to the natural world.” He extends his explanation of ecocriticism as “a response to needs, problems, or crisis, depending on one’s perception of urgency” (Dean 1994 p.1). Ecocriticism is a field that bridges the gap between literature and science.

This research is an effort to investigate the symbol of nature, as landscape as well as metaphor. It will effort to seem into the different ways in which life has combined in and has been anticipated by diverse writers in India. At the start of the 21st century, nature forces us to carry it to the center period. We must try to tackle the subject of life in this extraordinarily scientific and profitable world, through an investigation and scrutiny of modern Indian literature.

We discover impressions of nature study in the fiction of some post-World War-II, Bengali writers such as Manik Bandopadhyay, Advaita Mallabarman and Samaresh Basu in *A Boatman of Padma* (1936), *A River Called Titash* (1950) and *Ganga* (1957), respectively. All these novels are about rivers which equally maintain life and at times become destroyers of fishermen and boatmen. These tradesmen, through their effort and fight for livelihoods, redesign the daydream environment into a lively arena of social life. All the three novels portray the day to day resist for endurance and how this process of interdependence and collaboration between the fishermen, boatmen, small farmers, and their river centric environment influence each other’s survival. However, as Raymond Williams aptly points out, “when nature is separated out from the activities of men, it even ceases to be nature in any full and effective sense” (16).

Bhabani Bhattacharya’s *So Many Hungers* (1947), is a genuinely moving work of art. We discover in it an ingredient of eager inspection of men and life. It is about ache, fright, sadness, starvation, pain, and sacrifice, mainly due to man-made scarcity leading to the death of millions. He talks about the most sickening actual incident in the history of India, i.e., the Bengal famine of 1943. It is a heart-rending demonstration of the starvation for food, malnourishment, and ultimate death, the other face of nature. It is a lacerating description of the naked dreadfulness through cumulative details and absorbing story. It is about the difficulty of the two families living in the village of Baruni and Calcutta due to the starvation. The characters trust that they have been punished for their sins dedicated in the past. He deals with a parallel theme in *He Who Rides a Tiger*.

We also discover impressions of ecocriticism in Kamala Markandaya’s *Nectar in the Sieve*. But here the perception is contradictory, being the other face of nature. This novel deals with ‘The Flood,’ i.e., life trying to manage humans, it is in the ruined state. This leads to the pitiable and wretched conditions of the victims of the flood. When it became a danger to human lives, it is then that it became a substance of worldwide concern.

The Hungry Tide is a review on an endangered ecosystem- the Sundarbans in the Bay of Bengal. It is written by a flexible modern writer, Amitav Ghosh. The Sundarbans in the Bay of Bengal are some islands which people split with animals. The situation of their living is much lower for animals. The dilemma the inhabitants undergo due to unwanted, unexpected tidal surges and tiger attacks demonstrate a severe ecological disaster on earth. The reason is to generate alertness to assist organize action plans for the safety of the settlers.

Ghosh states that the environmental decline in the Sundarbans in his lifetime has been very noticeable and very shocking (Ferdous & Rutsch 51). Birdlife, crabs and fish, and individual trees and plants have incredibly uncommon, and their absence is felt. The loss of marine mammal

populations is part of this “catastrophe” (51). He feels there is “incredible urgency” to these ecological issues, and this comes out very evidently in the novel, contributing considerably to its ecological tone (51). One of his characters, Nirmal, watching his favorite landscape, is in no doubt that it is in dreadful decline:

Age teaches you to recognize the signs of death....

Now it was as if I could see those signs everywhere,
not just in myself, but in this place that I had lived in for
almost thirty years. The birds were vanishing,
the fish were dwindling, and from day to day,
the land was being reclaimed by the sea. (215)

Amitav Ghosh discusses the unstable life of people living in the Sundarbans. Christopher Rollason defines the novel as:

[an] exploration of the huge field of human communication,

testing both its opportunities and its limits as the characters seek to cross multiple barriers – the barriers of language, social class, and religion, and those between human beings and nature, between traditional and cosmopolitan India, between urban and rural, between India and the wider world. (2)

Thus, Amitav Ghosh’s novel is an idyllic illustration of a modern author grappling with literature’s perspective to address ecological issues.

Similarly, Raja Rao, one of the essential writers, has used the environmental setting in *Kanthapura* depicting the connection between man and nature. He uses rivers and mountains to highlight the significance of nature in man’s life. The temple, The river, and ‘Malgudi’ have an essential place in R.K.Narayan’s fiction. Moreover, Malgudi has been a backdrop to about ten novels by Narayan, becoming the ‘Hero’ in the words of Prof. Iyengar (Saxena 26).

We also discover glimpses of nature in the novel of Ruskin Bond, who lived in the flourishing green scenic surroundings of Dehradun and Mussoorie. His short stories reproduce his passionate belief in the nurturing feature of the environment. In the accounts for children like, ‘No Room for Leopard’, ‘Copperfield in the Jungle’, ‘An Island of Trees’, ‘The Tree Lover’, ‘The Cherry Tree’, and ‘All Creatures Great and Small’, which genuinely pursue their titles, explores themes like deforestation and its after-effects, saying no hunting, and the correlation of man and nature. He is compassionate towards nature, be it living or non-living.

Another significant writer of this age, writing about nature is Anita Desai. We find a sturdy existence of animals, plants, birds, and outside images of landscape in her psychological novels. It is attractive to a reminder that in her *Cry, the Peacock*, we are taken into the intellect of the character through the exterior landscape. This novel is a narrative of a lady Maya, who is not joyful after her marriage. She distinguishes herself with a peacock, which fights by its male partner before mating. Sadly this novel ends with Maya stirring her husband off the roof, finishing in his death. In *Clear Light of Day*, Monisha, the female protagonist, feels herself to be encaged like a wretched bird. Lastly, to increase liberty, she has to assign suicide. Anita Desai has also considered the problem of heartlessness towards animals and has used the landscape, particularly the mountains of Kanchenjunga, to tell the changing conditions or the mood in *The Inheritance of Loss*. The gloomy atmosphere of a child is reflected through Kanchenjunga, which is believed to have rewarded for the cruelty of human beings by losing its attractiveness. Her novel is apt for ecocritical study.

Thus, writers like Bhabani Bhattacharya, Ruskin Bond, Kamala Markandya, Amitav Ghosh, Raja Rao, R.K.Narayan, and Anita Desai, through their literature, have drawn concentration towards the representation of natural beauty as well as nature’s catastrophic face in the form of natural calamities like flood, famines, etc. These writers are longing to speak for the natural world

in literature. Many of them tried to portray what man has to damage nature, but few come up with suggestions as to how we can defeat or overturn the harm that has been done. Are a man and the writer a mute spectator, or just a responsive observer, or can he suggest what to do now? In our race towards modernity, are we competent in saving our natural landscape, or is it doomed for destruction? Lastly, it is, to a considerable extent, to be decided by a man who faces of nature he wants to see. Wordsworth could never have seen this countenance of life which the Indian writer sketches in these texts.

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